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Research Article

RISK FACTORS OF HEPATITIS C IN DISTRICT LAYYAH¹Sahrish Khan, ²Atiq-ur-Rehman, ²Muhammad Imran, ²Muhammad Hashim Raza¹University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, ²DHQ Hospital, Layyah**Abstract**

A study conducted in Layyah to determine the risk factors of hepatitis C. A cross sectional study was conducted at DHQ and asked about risk factors. The major causes of disease spread are unsafe blood transfusion, unsafe medical and surgical practices, ear and nose piercing, shaving at barbers, personal care items sharing, re-use of therapeutic syringes and unnecessary therapeutic injection. Because the disease is asymptomatic in its initial stage and most of the people are unaware of their health status. There are too many risk factors due to which our population is experiencing hepatitis C. So, we must inform people about risk factors to reduce the disease burden. Because, there is no post-exposure prophylaxis and no vaccine for HCV.

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INTRODUCTION:

In 1989 Hepatitis C virus (HCV) was discovered. HCV is cause of this silent disease. HCV promote chronic liver disease. Disease is asymptomatic at initial stage and people infected by HCV suffering from disease and do not know about it. HCV has been confessed as a major cause of serious liver disease throughout the world (1). WHO estimates that 170 million people are affected with chronic HCV infection worldwide (2). An estimated 366,000 deaths occur annually by HCV (3). Approximate 3–4 million persons are newly infected each year and 170 million persons are chronically infected with HCV (4,5). Among 70–80% of the patients, this virus continues to exist and replicate that leads toward chronic liver disease. Throughout the world, occurrence of HCV varies because of different behavioral, cultural, political, social and medical practices. Prevalence of infection is highest among both Africa and Asia; the industrialized nations in Australia, Northern and Western Europe and North America have low prevalence rate of HCV. In the developed world, populous nations with relatively low reported rates of HCV seroprevalence included France (1.1%), (6) Canada (0.8%), (7) and Australia (1.1%). (8,9) Germany (0.6%) (10). In the USA (1.8%) low, but slightly higher seroprevalence rate have been estimated. (11) Italy (2.2%) (12), Japan (1.5–2.3%), (13, 14) and China, whose population is one fifth of the world's population, 3.2% rate of HCV seroprevalence. (15) One community-based survey evaluated 0.9%. In India, which hold an additional one-fifth of the world's population. 2.1% rate reported in Indonesia, for voluntary blood donors serosurveys (16).

In Pakistan data exist for seroprevalence of HCV, where most appropriate rates extent between 2.4% and 6.5%. (17, 18,19) In the four provinces of Pakistan, Punjab is being highest reported for Prevalence of HCV. Pakistan medical and research council, conduct a recent survey in four provinces of Pakistan for prevalence of HCV as Punjab, Sindh, Balochistan and Khyberpakhtunkhwa 6.7%, 5%, 1.5% and 1.1% respectively (20, 21), When the infection at chronic phase then sudden end of HCV is infrequent. Affected people have liver fibrosis

because of chronic hepatitis C, after 10 to 40 years cirrhosis start in 15–25% of patients (22). Those who affected with CHC and cirrhosis are at high risk of liver failure and hepatocellular carcinoma (23).

OBJECTIVES:

- To find the risk factors among known cases of hepatitis C.
- To give recommendation for awareness of hepatitis C in general population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It was a cross sectional study including various risk factors of Hepatitis C conducted in Layyah (Punjab). Duration of study was six months. Population of study was the known cases of hepatitis C those come for treatment at healthcare facilities of district Layyah. Patients were asked about the risk factor against they were exposed in their past history. A structured questionnaire sheet was filled through direct personal interview with patients. There were asked 16 questions from the respondents. On the basis of these questions, patients were detected about the risk factors they were exposed. The collected data were organized, and analysed using SPSS, version 22. Frequencies and percentages were obtained and presented in the form of charts and groups. Ethical approval was taken for Ethical Review board of veterinary university, Lahore.

RESULTS:

There were taken 100 patients of hepatitis C and asked questions related to risk factors of hepatitis C. There were 60 female and 40 male patients. Majority of patients was from 40 years (20%) of age group followed by 45 years (12%) of age group. Risk factors were unsafe blood transfusions, unsafe medical and surgical practices, tattoos, ear and nose piercing, personal care items sharing, shaving at barbers, mother to new born baby, re-use of therapeutic syringes, teeth cleaned by dentist, and unnecessary therapeutic injections with 10%, 24%, 2%, 54%, 76%, 4%, 2%, 24% and 60% respectively. None of the participants have needle stick injury, injectable drug users, organ transplants, stay in prisons and sexual partner with hepatitis C.

Figure 1. Age of patients

Figure 2. Sex of the participants.

Figure 3. Blood transfusion and blood products

Table 1. Risk factors

Question	Frequency	Percentage
Had an organ transplant		
No	100	100.0
Have you undergone vaccination, medical procedure		
No	56	56.0
Yes	44	44.0
Surgery in last year		
No	76	76.0
Yes	24	24.0
Do you have any tattoos		
No	98	98.0
Yes	2	2.0
Body piercings		
No	46	46.0
Yes	54	54.0
Have you shared personal care items such as razors/toothbrushes/nail clippers		
No	24	24.0
Yes	76	76.0
Have you ever had a sexual partner with hepatitis C		
No	100	100.0
Family history or family member with Hepatitis C		
No	80	80.0
Yes	20	20.0
Did your mother have hepatitis C when you were born		
No	96	96.0
Yes	4	4.0

Figure 4. Needle sticks injury

Table 2. Risk factors

Question	Frequency	Percentage
Are you Injecting Drug Users		
No	100	100.0
Re use of syringes by GP clinic		
No	98	98.0
Yes	2	2.0
Do you have cleaned damage teeth by dentist?		
No	76	76.0
Yes	24	24.0
Do you have received unnecessary therapeutic injections?		
No	40	40.0
Yes	60	60.0
Are you in prisons?		
No	100	100.0

DISCUSSION:

This is the first study that thoroughly deals with the risk factors of the HCV infection in Layyah. Our study conducted prevalence of hepatitis C through blood transfusion, received blood products was 10%. Our risk rates are different from others. This result goes contrary to that reported in Africa (24) who found 0.03% prevalence of hepatitis C virus. But this rate is high than that reported in Pakistan 3.0% (25). Transmission of hepatitis C virus from mother to child was 4% in our record. This result is similar to other reported rate (26). In our investigation, there were no known case of hepatitis C that was injecting

drug user. 79.4% of HCV infected persons shared syringes and needles in Scotland (27). The lower percentage we found in this case, may be patients are trying to hide that they belong to such a part of society. Among injection drug users who do not share syringes, an important proportion of HCV infections may be attributed to cooker/cotton sharing. (28) In our research, dental treatment was a main risk factor for currency of HCV infection 24%. It is generally accepted that dental treatment can be an infection transmit, from dentist to patient, from patient to dentist and from patient to patient. This finding is similar to other research. (29) Respondents were

more likely to make frequent use of certain personal protective equipment was 76%. Which is like to (30) Patients without Organ transplantation were analysed. So, this risk factor was not found for hepatitis C infection in this study. Contradicts results were conducted in United States (31). Researchers reported about chronic hepatitis C virus infection could be spread. Needle stick injury as risk factor for prevalence of hepatitis C infection was 4%. Low rate evaluate in Germany 0.4 – 0.7% (32). Higher rate of NSIs, ranging from 22% to 59%. This is consistent with our findings (33). Tattoos as mentioned for risk factor was 2 %. But our finding is not compared with others (34) He said Tattoos applied in unregulated settings have been linked to such transmission. But in regulated settings have not been associated with HCV transmission. We had taken sexual histories from patients. Their Sexual partner was not affected with hepatitis C of all respondents. Therefore, sexual activity as risk factors was not spreading of infection. Our report was also similar to others (35). He concluded through sex HCV infection was not efficiently transmitted. Contrary results found by (36,37,38) especially, people who have infected with HIV, transmission of HCV through sex can occur. It has been reported MSM with HIV infection have greater chances for chronic HCV infection in New York City and Boston, along with multiple European cities Major risk of HCV associated with unnecessary therapeutic injection was 60%. The study conducted in Pakistan reported that 72% of the patients receive unnecessary therapeutic injections. This rate is lower in Layyah. Pakistan was reported as one of the countries with the highest frequency of injection use in the world with an average of more than 9 injections per person annually. (39,40)

CONCLUSION:

Risk factors for HCV transmission in Layyah are different as compared to other areas. There are too many risk factors due to which our population is experiencing hepatitis C. we have to control our risk factors. We should informed people about risk factors, so that they can be careful about it. Therefore Silent killer, Hepatitis C virus will not be transmitted in next generation. Reducing HCV infection, can be a major public health challenge.

REFERENCES:

- Perz JF, Armstrong GL, Farrington LA, Hutin YJ, Bell BP (2006) The contributions of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus infections to cirrhosis and primary liver cancer worldwide. *J Hepatol* 45(4): 529- 538
- Previsani N, Lavanchy D (2002) Hepatitis B. World Health Organization
- WHO/CDS/CSR/LYO/2002.2, Geneva.
- Perz JF, Armstrong GL, Farrington LA, Hutin YJ, Bell BP (2006) The contributions of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus infections to cirrhosis and primary liver cancer worldwide. *J Hepatol* 45(4): 529- 538.
- Hepatitis B.1.* Geneva, World Health Organization, 2000 (WHO Fact sheet, no. 204).
- Hepatitis C.2.* Geneva, World Health Organization, 2000 (WHO Fact sheet, no. 164)
- Desenclos JC. Epidemiology of hepatitis C. *Revue du Praticien* 2000; **50**: 1066–70
- Zou S, Tepper M, El Saadany S. Prediction of hepatitis C burden in Canada. *Can J Gastroenterol* 2000; **14**: 575–80
- Law MG, Dore GJ, Bath N, et al. Modelling hepatitis C virus incidence, prevalence, and long-term sequelae in Australia, 2001. *Int J Epidemiol* 2003; **32**: 717–724
- Australian census, 2001, total population. <http://www.abs.gov.au/ausstats/abs%40census.nsf/ddc9b4f92657325cca256c3e000bdbaf/7dd97c937216e32fca256bbe008371f0!OpenDocument#CensusCounts> (accessed July 25, 2005).
- Palitzsch KD, Hottentrager B, Schlottmann K, et al. Prevalence of antibodies against hepatitis C virus in the adult German population. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 1999; **11**: 1215–20.
- Alter MJ, Kruszon-Moran D, Nainan OV, et al. The prevalence of hepatitis C virus infection in the United States, 1988 through 1994. *N Engl J Med* 1999; **341**: 556–62.
- Puro V, Petrosillo N, Ippolito G, Aloisi MS, Boumis E, Rava L. Occupational hepatitis C virus infection in Italian health care workers. *Am J Public Health* 1995; **85**: 1272–75.
- Ohshima S, Komatsu M, Nakane K, et al. Iatrogenic GB virus C/hepatitis G virus infection in an area endemic for hepatitis C virus. *J Hosp Infect* 2000; **44**: 179–85
- Hayashi J, Nakashima K, Yoshimura E, Hirata M, Maeda Y, Kashiwagi S. Detection of HCV RNA in subjects with antibody to hepatitis C virus among the general population of Fukuoka. *Jpn J Gastroenterol* 1994; **29**: 147–51. **564**
- Xia GL, Liu CB, Cao HL, et al. Prevalence of hepatitis B and C virus infections in the general Chinese population: results from a nationwide cross-sectional seroepidemiologic study of hepatitis A, B, C, D, and E virus infections in China, 1992. *International Hepatology Communications* 1996; **5**: 62–73.
- Sulaiman HA, Julitasari, Sie A, et al. Prevalence of hepatitis B and C viruses in healthy Indonesian blood donors. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 1995; **89**: 167–70.

17. Mujeeb SA, Shahab S, Hyder AA. Geographical display of health information: study of hepatitis C infection in Karachi, Pakistan. *Public Health* 2000. **114**: 413–15.
18. Luby SP, Qamruddin K, Shah AA, et al. The relationship between therapeutic injections and high prevalence of hepatitis C infection in Hafizabad, Pakistan. *Epidemiol Infect* 1997; **119**: 349–56.
19. Khattak MF, Salamat N, Bhatti FA, Qureshi TZ. Seroprevalence of hepatitis B, C and HIV in blood donors in northern Pakistan. *JPak Med Assoc* 2002; **52**: 398–402.
20. Ali SA, Donahue RM, Qureshi H, Vermund SH (2009) Hepatitis B and hepatitis C in Pakistan: prevalence and risk factors. *Int J Infect Dis* 13(1): 9-19.
21. Mirza S (2010) Growing epidemic of hepatitis C: Lack of awareness among masses. Medpedia, San Francisco, USA
22. Lauer GM, Walker BD. Hepatitis C virus infection. *N Engl J Med* 2001; **345**: 41–52
23. El-Serag HB. Epidemiology of viral hepatitis and hepatocellular carcinoma. *Gastroenterology*
24. Apata IW, Averbhoff F, Pitman J, Bjork A, Yu J, Amin NA, et al. Progress toward prevention of transfusion-transmitted hepatitis B and hepatitis C infection—sub-Saharan Africa, 2000–2011. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*. 2014; **63**: 613–9.
25. Umar M, Bushra H, Ahmad M, Khurram M, Usman S, et al. (2010) Hepatitis C in Pakistan: a review of available data. *Hepat Mon* 10(3): 205-214
26. Resti, M., Azzari, C., Lega, L., Rossi, M. E., Zammarchi, E., Novembre, E., & Vierucci, A. (1995). Mother-to-infant transmission of hepatitis C virus. *Acta Paediatrica*, **84**(3), 251-255.
27. Palmateer N, Hutchinson S, McAllister G, Munro A, Cameron S, Goldberg D, Taylor A (2014) Risk of transmission associated with sharing drug injecting paraphernalia: analysis of recent hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection using cross-sectional survey data. *J Viral Hepat* 21:25-32
28. *Am J Public Health*. 2001
29. Mahboobi N, Porter SR, Karayiannis P, Alavian SM (2013) Dental treatment as a risk factor for hepatitis B and C viral infection. A review of the recent literature. *J Gastrointest Liver Dis* 22:79-86
30. H. Chemaitelly, K. Chaabna, and L. J. Abu-Raddad, “The epidemiology of hepatitis C virus in the fertile crescent: systematic review and meta-analysis,” *PLoS ONE*, vol. 10, no. 8, Article Id0135281, 2015.
31. Dultz G, Graubard BI, Martin P, Welker M-W, Vermehren J, Zeuzem S, et al. (2017) Liver transplantation for chronic hepatitis C virus infection in the United States 2002±2014::1531-1537
32. Hoffmann, C., Buchholz, L., & Schnitzler, P. (2013). Reduction of needlestick injuries in healthcare personnel at a university hospital using safety devices. *Journal of occupational medicine and toxicology*, **8**(1), 20.
33. Salzer HJF, Hoenigl M, Kessler HH, et al: Lack of risk-awareness and reporting behaviour towards HIV infection through needlestick injury among European medical students. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2011; **214**: 407–410.
34. Tohme RA, Holmberg SD. Transmission of hepatitis C virus infection through tattooing and piercing: a critical review. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2012; **54**: 1167–78. [PubMed: 22291098]
35. Tohme RA, Holmberg SD. Is sexual contact a major mode of hepatitis C virus transmission? *Hepatology*. 2010; **52**: 1497–505. [PubMed: 20635398]
36. Garg S, Taylor LE, Grasso C, et al. Prevalent and incident hepatitis C virus infection among HIV-infected men who have sex with men engaged in primary care in a Boston community health center. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2013; **56**: 1480–7. [PubMed: 23386630]
37. Fierer DS, Mullen MP, Dieterich DT, et al. Early-onset liver fibrosis due to primary hepatitis C virus infection is higher over time in HIV-infected men. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2012; **55**: 887–9. [PubMed: 22677713]
38. Dionne-Odom J, Osborn MK, Radziewicz H, et al. Acute hepatitis C and HIV coinfection. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2009; **9**: 775–83. [PubMed: 19926037]
39. Jafri W, Jafri N, Yakoob J, Islam M, Tirmizi SFI, et al. (2006) Hepatitis B and C: prevalence and risk factors associated with seropositivity among children in Karachi, Pakistan. *BMC Infect Dis* 6:101.
40. Khan AJ, Luby SP, Fikree F, Karim A, Obaid S, et al. (2000) Unsafe injections and the transmission hepatitis B and C in a periurban community in Pakistan. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 78 (8): 956-963.
41. Mother-to-infant transmission of hepatitis C virus. *Acta Paediatr* 1995; **84**: 251-5.
42. Varan, Aiden K. “Hepatitis C Seroprevalence Among Prison Inmates Since 2001: Still High but Declining” *Public Health Reports* March-April Volume 129: (2014): 187-195
43. Wicker S, Ludwig A-M, Gottschalk R, Rabenau

HF: Needlestick injuries among healthcare personnels: occupational hazard or avoidable hazard? *Wien Klin Wochenschr* 2008, 120:486–492.

44. Hagan H, Des Jarlais DC, Friedman SR, Purchase D, Alter MJ. Reduced risk of hepatitis B and hepatitis C among participants in the Tacoma syringe exchange. *Am J Public Health*. 1995;85